

System of Wheat Intensification (SWI): A Novel Approach

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Summary

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) is the most extensively grown cereal crop in the world, covering about 237 million hectares annually, accounting for a total of 420 million tonnes. Wheat stands second in grain production in the world and most widely cultivated food. SWI is a new concept and goes with the SRI principle. It can reduce weeding time to one-third and to one-half of the time needed for current weeding practice. Herbicide use is effective with SWI, but farmers are inventing or modifying tools that reduce the labour time required for weeding. Thus, SWI is a methodology aimed at increasing the yield of wheat, where all agronomic principles are put into practices to provide high wheat yield per drop of water and per kg of agricultural inputs like fertilizer, seed etc.

Introduction

System of wheat intensification is following the principle of system of Rice intensification. If we discuss about condition of Rice-Wheat cropping system in north India approximately 10-million-hectare area covered by this cropping system. It is possible only by using rigorous inputs like vigorous seeds, inorganic fertilizers, weedicide, Insecticide, Pesticides etc. If these inputs are not used proper and balanced; it might cause detrimental effect on environment, soil rhizosphere as well as on production and productivity of land. For intensify wheat production and productivity, SWI is great approach to now scenario. The system of wheat intensification has high probability to contribute enhance wheat production in per single unit of water and per kg of farm resources like seeds, inorganic and organic fertilizer etc., and also follow the principle of SRI technology of Rice production (Dhar *et al.*, 2014). This methodology of wheat cultivation can increase yield by two to three times through some improvements in crop management factors. This technology was already evaluated and demonstrated in some countries in the world including India.

The System of Wheat Intensification (SWI) was tested first time by Farmers in Goundam and Dire, Timbuktu, Mali in 2009. In 2008, some first trials with SWI were initiated, comparing transplanting of young wheat seedlings (with wide spacing, small but regular applications of water, increased organic matter, etc.) with direct-seeding and with controls (traditional broadcasting of seed to establish the crop. In this area, given the heat and wind of the winter season which cause desiccation in plants, direct extrapolation of SRI methods to wheat in this area, i.e., transplanting young seedlings, produced poorer results than conventional practice. However, a direct-seeded version of SWI gave 13% higher yield, with 30-40% less labour. The productivity of labour with this method (yield per hour of labour input) went up by 75%, and 25-30% less water was required.

Principles of SWI

SWI is mainly based on the following two principles of crop production:

1. Principle of Root Development: Healthy root development is an important factor for healthy growth of a plant. Conventionally, Wheat seeds are sown in a closer manner i.e., no specific space is maintained between the seeds leading to competition between the roots of the plants for nutrients, water and sunlight. The weed population will be higher because of closer spacing, thereby increasing the number of competitors for the resources (Kaur,2012). Root growth inhibition is promoted by crowding leading to poor resistance for the weeds. SWI technology involves proper plant spacing, roots of the plants get proper space to spread out, better nourishment, better light, more oxygen and the soil quality is also improved by the period of time leading to higher number of effective tillers, higher yields and better nutritive quality.

2. Principle of intensive Care: The plant growth is usually hampered by many biotic and abiotic factors, major factors include improper nutrients and water availability, poor water and nutrients quality, disease incidence, Insects/pests and weeds. Principle of intensive care does not support higher number of plant population per unit area rather it holds up with proper space maintenance and close monitoring and care of the plants. This can be done by adopting Good Agricultural practices, time to time soil and water testing and close monitoring of the plants.

Why SWI is Needed?

The SWI is an adaptation of techniques used in the SRI. SRI has been successfully practiced in 35 countries worldwide. In terms of agricultural productivity, the sustainability of the farming system is an important issue. More than 10 million hectares under rice-wheat cropping system in North India is one of the most intensively cultivated areas in the world, which is possible only through the use of more intensive inputs like seeds, chemical fertilizers, herbicides, plant protection chemicals etc. Imbalanced use of external inputs particularly agrochemicals (fertilizer, fungicides, pesticides, herbicides) might cause deleterious effect on the soil and environment, as well as on the system productivity.

Package of Practices for SWI

Similar to that of SRI technology, SWI also requires quality seeds as well as special agronomic management practices. Details of wheat cultivation with SWI technology has given below:

Land preparation: Prior to final land preparation (15- 20 days ahead) 2.0 t FYM or 0.4 t of vermin-compost per acre of land should be applied. If the soil does not have appropriate moisture, irrigate before ploughing. Before the last ploughing, broadcast 27 kg DAP (4.86 kg N and 12.42 kg P₂O₅) and 13.5 kg potash per acre of land. However, the doses of nutrients are highly variable depending upon the yield target. The fertilizer (both organic and inorganic) requirement during land preparation and top dressing can be determined using the nutrient decision support systems such as “Nutrient Expert®” (Majumder *et al.*, 2014).

Seed selection and treatment: Only healthy seeds of right variety suitable for a particular locality should be selected for sowing. There should not be any mixture of seeds of other varieties of weeds. Always certified seed, purchased from a reliable source.

Seed treatment: The following inputs are required: Improved seed (10 kg), 20 liters warm water (60°C), Vermicompost (5 kg), Gur (4 kg), Cow urine (4 liters), and Bavistin (20 g).

Seed Treatment Process

According to PRADAN (2012) the following steps are to be taken sequentially.

1. Separate foreign materials from 10 kg seed (if any).
2. Take 20 liters of warm water (up to 60°C) in a vessel.
3. Put the seed material in the warm water.
4. Remove the floating seeds (chaffy in nature) from the warm water. Add 5 kg vermin-compost, 4 kg gur and 4 liters of cow urine, and keep the mixture for 8 hours.
5. Separate the seed mixture from the solution, and then sieving it through a cotton cloth after 8 hours.
6. Add 20 g Bavistin to the seed mixture and keep this for 12 hours in a wet jute bag for germination and for subsequent sowing.

Sowing

The sprouted seeds will be used for sowing in the field by dibbling using two seeds per hill. Different row to row and plant to plant spacing (15 cm × 15 cm or 20 cm × 20 cm) can be used depending on the moisture content. A manually driven or motorized seed drill can be used for sowing. Seeds will be sown at a depth of 2.5–3.0 cm using a dibbler or pegs. Wherever the seed failed to germinate or destroyed, the gaps were filled with germinated seeds within 10 days of sowing.

Irrigation

Phase-wise irrigation management should be as follows. First irrigation is done 15 days after sowing (DAS) to trigger root initiation. Otherwise, unavailability of moisture in soil will prevent root initiation. Second

irrigation is given at 25 DAS, results in emerging a greater number of tillers. Third irrigation is given at 35-40 DAS. Subsequent irrigations are given at 60, 80 and 100 DAS, depending on soil and climatic conditions. During the flowering and grain-filling stage, appropriate moisture should be available in the soil.

Weed Management

Hoeing is essential component of SWI since it ruins the weeds that compete with crop for space, light, water and nutrients. Weeding through hoeing loosens the soils and effectively aerates the roots, allowing exploration of soil that leads to better water and nutrients absorption from deeper soil depth.

Table 1. Comparison between traditional wheat cultivation and system of wheat intensification:

Particulars	Traditional cultivation	SWI
Seed rate	100-125 kg/ha	20-30 kg/ha
Seed treatment	Not done	With cow urine and fungicide
Sowing	Broadcasting	Line sowing
Spacing	No spacing regulation	20 cm × 20 cm
Weeding/hoeing	Not done	3 times
Length of panicle	10-11 cm	15 cm
No. of grains/panicle	18-50	60-120
No. of panicles/hill	Mostly 1-2, Good stand 2-4	20-45
Yield	1 – 2 t/ha	3 – 4 t/ha

Source: ATMA (2008); PRADAN (2012).

Advantages of SWI

1. More number of effective tillers.
2. No lodging of crop and increased production.
3. Early anthesis and crop maturity (4-5 days).
4. Long and shining grain is obtained good grain quality.
5. More fodder available for cattle.
6. No/ lesser disease incidence and insect infestation.
7. Less seed requirement 75-80% seed saving (Only 20-25 kg/ha).
8. Weeding facilitated good aeration to roots.
9. Less water requirement (20-30%).

Constraints in SWI

1. Need to design and develop suitable sowing implement.
2. Availability of suitable weeder to the farmers.
3. Capacity building of farmers in adoption of SWI.
4. To ensure irrigation at critical stages of crop growth.
5. Intensive scientific study need to be done at research station.

Conclusion

In conclusion, System of Wheat Intensification Method of wheat cultivation has shown positively response on all measured growth parameters, yield characters and yield production compared to conventional method. It shows positive response for seed treatment and wider space sowing. The SWI technology has already established its strength in terms of multiple benefits like enhanced productivity per unit land, water and other inputs with higher economic gain. However, more detail study is needed on various agronomic and other bio-physical changes in the plants under SWI method. Finally, more skill oriented training for the SWI farmers is required to build up their confidence.

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